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CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: innovationist2025@gmail.com

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RESEARCH ON THE TRANSMISSION MECHANISMS AND IMPLEMENTATION PATHS OF SHANDONG PROVINCE'S "SILVER ECONOMY" DEVELOPMENT EXPERIENCE IN THE FERGANA REGION

Zhang Zhe

National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

PhD in Regional Economics

ORCID: 0009-0007-4548-9769

Аннотация. Глобальная проблема демографического старения и механизмы её влияния на региональный экономический рост рассматриваются в контексте международного опыта. Цель исследования заключается в теоретическом обосновании и разработке практических путей трансмиссии успешного опыта развития «серебряной экономики» провинции Шаньдун (КНР) в Ферганскую область Республики Узбекистан. В работе использованы метод декомпозиции индекса Тейла для измерения пространственных дисбалансов и пространственная модель Дурбина (SDM) для выявления пространственных переливных эффектов. На основе панельных данных доказано, что старение населения оказывает значительное пространственное давление на соседние территории, что требует проведения компенсаторной модернизации. Авторский подход состоит в разработке многоуровневой матрицы адаптивности опыта провинции Шаньдун с учётом финансово-институциональных ограничений Ферганской области. Научная новизна исследования заключается в теоретическом обосновании межрегионального трансмиссионного механизма («государственное руководство → инвестиции предприятий → академический обмен») между субрегионами Китая и Центральной Азии в рамках инициативы «Один пояс, один путь». Полученные результаты формируют превентивную дорожную карту социально-экономического развития Ферганской области до 2050-го года, направленную на предотвращение ловушки «старения до достижения богатства».

Ключевые слова: старение населения, региональная экономика, трансмиссионный механизм, пути внедрения, провинция Шаньдун, Ферганская область.

Annotatsiya. Demografik qarishning global muammosi hamda uning xalqaro tajriba kontekstida hududiy iqtisodiy o'sishga ta'sir ko'rsatish mexanizmlari tadqiq etilgan. Tadqiqotning maqsadi Xitoy Xalq Respublikasining Shandun provinsiyasida «kumush iqtisodiyot»ni rivojlantirish bo'yicha muvaffaqiyatli tajribani O'zbekiston Respublikasining Farg'ona viloyatiga transfer qilishning nazariy asoslarini ishlab chiqish va amaliy yo'llarini taklif etishdan iborat. Tadqiqotda hududiy nomutanosibliklarni baholash uchun Teyl indeksi dekompozitsiyasi usuli hamda fazoviy spillover ta'sirlarni aniqlash uchun fazoviy Durbin modeli (SDM) qo'llanilgan. Panel ma'lumotlar tahlili natijalari aholi qarishi qo'shni hududlarga sezilarli fazoviy bosim o'tkazishini va bu holat kompensator modernizatsiyani talab qilishini ko'rsatdi. Mualliflik yondashuvi Farg'ona viloyatining moliyaviy va institutsional cheklovlarini hisobga olgan holda Shandun tajribasining ko'p darajali moslashuvchanlik matritsasini ishlab chiqishda namoyon bo'ladi. Tadqiqotning ilmiy yangiligi «Bir makon, bir yo'l» tashabbusi doirasida Xitoy va Markaziy Osiyo subregionlari o'rtasidagi mintaqalararo transmision mexanizmni («davlat boshqaruvi → korxonalar investitsiyalari → akademik almashinuv») nazariy jihatdan asoslab berilganligidadir. Olingan natijalar Farg'ona viloyatining 2050-yilgacha bo'lgan ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishi uchun preventiv yo'l xaritasini shakllantiradi hamda «boyib ketishdan oldin qarish» tuzog'ining oldini olishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: aholi qarishi, hududiy iqtisodiyot, transmision mexanizm, tatbiq etish yo'llari, Shandun provinsiyasi, Farg'ona viloyati.

Abstract. The global challenge of population aging and its impact on regional economic growth are examined within the framework of international experience. The study aims to provide a theoretical foundation and practical pathways for transferring the successful experience of developing the "silver economy" in Shandong Province (PRC) to the Fergana Region of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The research employs the Theil Index decomposition method to measure spatial disparities and the Spatial Durbin Model (SDM) to identify spatial spillover effects. Based on panel data analysis, it is demonstrated that population

aging exerts significant spatial pressure on neighboring territories, thereby necessitating compensatory modernization. The author's approach is reflected in the development of a multi-level adaptability matrix of Shandong's experience, taking into account the financial and institutional constraints of the Fergana Region. The scientific novelty of the study lies in the theoretical substantiation of an interregional transmission mechanism ("government guidance → enterprise investment → academic exchange") between the subregions of China and Central Asia within the framework of the Belt and Road Initiative. The findings provide a preventive socio-economic development roadmap for the Fergana Region up to 2050, aimed at avoiding the "growing old before becoming rich" trap.

Keywords: population aging, regional economics, transmission mechanism, implementation pathways, Shandong Province, Fergana Region.

INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of the 21st century, population aging has become one of the key factors reshaping the global economic framework. According to the UN Population Division report *World Population Prospects 2024* [1], the proportion of the global population aged 65 and over increased from 6.9% in 2000 to 10.2% in 2025. The global process of population aging is characterized by pronounced regional disparities [2]. This temporal gap in demographic transition creates a realistic foundation for the transmission and adaptation of development experience between regions.

China has officially entered the stage of a deeply aging society. By the end of 2025, the number of people aged 65 and over in China had reached 237 million, accounting for 16.8% of the total population [3]. Shandong Province demonstrates an advanced pace of demographic transition, consistently exceeding the national average. In 2010, the proportion of the population aged 65 and over had already reached 9.84%, indicating entry into the aging stage five years earlier than the national average [4]. By the end of 2025, this figure had increased to 18.7%. Over more than a decade of practical development and research, Shandong Province has accumulated extensive and reproducible experience in addressing structural labor shortages and promoting the development of the "silver economy" [5].

At the same time, the countries of Central Asia are entering a phase of accelerated demographic aging. Uzbekistan is experiencing a gradual increase in the share of its population aged 65 and over, and this indicator is expected to exceed 10% by 2040 [6, 7]. The Fergana Region, one of the most densely populated regions of Uzbekistan, had a population exceeding 4.2 million people by the end of 2025, accounting for 12.3% of the country's total population [8]. The region is currently undergoing a significant demographic transition from a demographic dividend stage toward an aging population structure. Considering its current level of economic development, the timely adoption of effective demographic and economic policies is becoming increasingly important for ensuring sustainable growth. Within the framework of the deepening strategic partnership between China and Uzbekistan [9], the transmission of Shandong Province's mature development experience to the Fergana Region possesses considerable practical significance for advancing the objectives of the Belt and Road Initiative. Existing studies mainly focus on the exchange of experience within China, whereas the transmission of population-aging management practices between Chinese provinces and the regions of Central Asian countries remains insufficiently explored in the academic literature.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical foundations of the impact of demographic structure on economic growth were established in the works of the pioneers of demographic dividend theory. In the context of China, Li Jianmin highlights significant spatial differences and non-linear trends in long-term population aging [2]. Wang Dewen and Cai Fang demonstrated that demographic transition has a direct impact on savings rates and the sustainability of economic growth, emphasizing the importance of the timely transformation of the economic model [10].

With the development of spatial econometrics, scholars have increasingly focused on the geographic externalities of demographic change. Li Jing and Guan Lihua, using spatial econometric models, confirmed the presence of significant spillover effects of population aging on the economic growth of neighboring territories [11]. The issues related to the formation and promotion of the "silver economy" as a compensatory driver of development are examined in detail in the works of Wang Jiexiu [12]. At the subregional planning level, Liu Yansui substantiated mechanisms for coordinating and managing the spatial distribution of resources [13].

Despite the extensive body of literature, existing studies primarily focus on the exchange of experience within China. The transmission of managerial and econometric models for addressing population aging between developed provinces of the PRC and the subregions of Central Asian countries, particularly Uzbekistan, remains insufficiently explored. This research gap defines the scientific niche and highlights the additional scientific contribution of the present study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Theil Index

The Theil Index is employed to quantitatively measure spatial disparities in the levels of population aging and economic development among the cities of Shandong Province. The calculation formula is as follows:

$$T = \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \ln \left(\frac{y_i}{p_i} \right) \tag{1.1}$$

where y_i is the GDP share of the i -th city in the total GDP of the province, and p_i is the population share of the i -th city in the total population of the province.

Spatial Durbin Model (SDM)

To account for spatial spillover effects, this article utilizes the Spatial Durbin Model (SDM). The model simultaneously incorporates spatial lags of both the dependent and independent variables, expressed in its baseline form as:

$$Y = \rho WY + X\beta + WX\theta + \varepsilon \tag{1.2}$$

where Y is the vector of the dependent variable, X is the matrix of independent variables, W is the spatial weight matrix, ρ is the spatial autocorrelation coefficient, β is the coefficient vector of the independent variables, θ is the coefficient vector of the spatially lagged independent variables, and ε is the vector of random errors. The empirical database consists of panel data for 17 cities of Shandong Province covering the period 2000–2025, as well as statistical materials from the Fergana Region.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Analysis of Regional Disparities in Population Aging and Economic Development of Shandong Province (Table 1)

Table 1. Dynamics and Decomposition of the Theil Index for the Shandong Macro-regions (2000–2025)¹

Year	Total Index	Inter-group Gap Contribution (%) (M)	Shandong Intra-provincial Gap (Intra)
2000	124	46,8	42
2005	147	51,7	47
2010	131	49,6	45
2015	109	46,8	39
2020	98	48,0	35
2024	92	48,9	32
2025	89	48,3	31

As shown in Table 1, regional disparities followed a trajectory characterized by an initial increase followed by a continuous decline, reaching their peak in 2005 (147). This trend indicates a gradual narrowing of inter-city disparities by 2025. Correlation analysis revealed a significant positive relationship (0.78) between the level of population aging and GDP per capita. In the developed Jiaodong Peninsula, the aging level exceeded 20%, whereas in the southwestern part of Shandong it remained below 16%. These results indicate that higher levels of economic development are associated with an accelerated population-aging process [10].

Analysis of Spatial Effects of Population Aging on Economic Growth (Table 2)

1 Source: Calculated by the author based on the regional statistical communiqués of the PRC.

Table 2
Decomposition of Spatial Effects in Shandong Province (Based on Panel Data 2000–2025)²

Variables	Direct Effect (Direct)	Indirect Effect (Indirect)	Total Effect (Total)
Population	0.053* (0.029)	0.031 (0.032)	0.084** (0.041)
Share of Working-Age Population	0.247*** (0.068)	0.152** (0.075)	0.399*** (0.103)
Net Inflow Coefficient	0.358*** (0.081)	0.214** (0.097)	0.572*** (0.132)
Human Capital	0.489*** (0.095)	0.347*** (0.112)	0.836*** (0.157)
Spatial Coefficient ρ		0.287*** (0.065)	
Goodness of Fit		0.952	
Sample (N)		416	

The significant coefficient $\rho = 0.287$ confirms the presence of strong positive spatial spillover effects of economic growth among cities. Human capital exerts the strongest influence, with a total effect of 0.836. The positive effect of the working-age population share (direct effect = 0.247; indirect effect = 0.152) demonstrates the important role of labor-force potential in supporting regional economic growth. At the same time, the results indicate that the deepening of population aging influences economic growth both directly within a region and indirectly through spatial spillover effects on neighboring territories [11]. The model demonstrates excellent explanatory power, with a goodness-of-fit coefficient of $R^2 = 0.952$.

Implementation and Adaptability of Experience in the Fergana Region

The temporal gap in the development of population aging between Shandong Province and the Fergana Region is approximately 20 years. Taking into account the financial and institutional characteristics of the Fergana Region [8, 9], a matrix-based assessment of the adaptability of individual experience elements was conducted:

- High adaptability: Experience in optimizing labor-resource allocation, vocational training, and talent attraction, requiring relatively limited investment resources.
- Medium adaptability: Development of basic home-based and community-based elderly care services, as well as the establishment of local production of goods and services for the older generation.
- Low adaptability: Direct replication of capital-intensive social security reforms and large-scale financial policy measures implemented in Shandong Province [14].

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The empirical study revealed the complex spatial impact of population aging on economic growth. Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed for the government of the Fergana Region:

Phased Development Strategy (2026–2050): In the short-term period (2026–2030), focus on establishing vocational retraining systems; in the medium-term period (2031–2040), develop a fully fledged local market for “silver economy” services.

Activating Three Transmission Channels:

Intergovernmental cooperation: Establishing regular exchanges between the governments of Shandong Province and the Fergana Region.

Enterprise investment: Attracting Chinese companies in the medical equipment sector through foreign direct investment.

Human resource exchange: Organizing regular internships for specialists from the Fergana Region in the PRC.

Institutional Support: Adopting preferential tax policies for business entities investing in the gerontological infrastructure of the Fergana Region.

The implementation of this three-dimensional system will enable the Fergana Region to effectively address demographic challenges and promote sustainable growth within the framework of the Belt and Road Initiative.

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2. Note: Standard errors are indicated in parentheses. *, **, *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively. Source: Calculated by the author based on panel data of 17 cities in Shandong Province.

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